

The role of spirituality and religiosity on the suicide ideation and depressive symptoms of middle to old age brazilian homeless individuals

Ravan Abner Rosa¹, Flávio Teixeira Carvalho¹, Cloe de Oliveira Massa¹, Ana Carolina Scurato Testa¹, Luciano Magalhães Vitorino², Giancarlo Lucchetti³

¹ Discente, Faculdade de Medicina de Itajubá

² Docente, Faculdade de Medicina de Itajubá

³ Docente, Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16739669>

RESUMO:

Objective: To investigate the association among S/R, suicidal ideation, and depressive symptoms among middle-to-old-aged Brazilian homeless individuals. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study included 162 individuals aged 50 years or over from the city of São Paulo, Brazil. Suicidal ideation was assessed using item 9 of the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), and depressive symptoms were evaluated using the total score for the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). Religiosity was measured by the Duke Religion Index (DUREL), spirituality by the FACIT-Sp-12, and spiritual/religious coping (SRC) by the BriefRCOPE scale. Both adjusted logistic and linear regression analyses were conducted to examine the associations. **Results:** Participants had a mean age of 58.45 years (SD = 5.89), being 79% males and 55.6% divorced/separated or widowed (55.6%). Suicidal ideation was reported by 19.8% of the sample, and 42% exhibited significant depressive symptoms. Higher levels of spiritual wellbeing (both “Meaning” and “Peace”) and intrinsic religiosity, were significantly associated with lower levels of depressive symptoms. Additionally, higher levels of meaning was inversely associated with suicidal ideation. In contrast, higher negative religious/spiritual coping was significantly associated with both increased suicidal ideation and depressive symptoms. **Conclusion:** Religiosity and spirituality appear to play dual roles in the mental health of middle-to-old-aged homeless individuals, acting as either protective or risk factors depending on the nature of their use. These findings highlight the importance of considering religious and spiritual dimensions in public health strategies and suggest the need for tailored interventions that integrate S/R into mental health and social care policies.

Keywords: Aged; Religion and psychology; Suicidal ideation; Depression; Homeless persons.

Organização:

Biblioteca Prof. Dr. Eurípedes Garcia

Coordenação de TCC FMIT